

A Win-Win-Win Path for Flight Safety, Health, and Corporate Profits

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ABBREVIATIONS

INEP International Network for Epidemiology in Policy

ABSTRACT

When evidence of harm mounts and denial dominates thus suppressing truth, health scientists must work to defend those harmed and prevent future harms. Their advocating for truth would result in improved safety and health for crew and passengers, and crises would be minimized. Other implicated parties include those dominating policy usually with a financial interest; responsible action from them would result in enhanced reputation with commensurate business advantages; it also would result in reduced economic burdens from compensatory damages. Those with responsibility for aircraft maintenance and insurance also would be spared cost overruns. Human rights and justice must prevail.

Context of this keynote address

Epidemiology is the science of population health and well-being. Epidemiologists study the distribution and determinants of disease in populations and apply the knowledge gained to the control of health problems. The focus is on preventing harms to populations (i.e., morbidity; premature mortality; and well-being). Epidemiology is, in fact, the applied science that informs rational health policy by bridging toxicology (results from animal experiments) to the human response to toxicants.

Epidemiological analysis and interpretation of data can result in controversy. Reports based on poor science, or misleading reports from special interest groups, can foment uncertainty, confuse the public and policy-makers, and lead to delayed or damaging policies that negatively impact people and the living systems on which they depend.

The *International Network for Epidemiology in Policy* (INEP), formerly known as the *International Joint Policy Committee of the Societies of Epidemiology* (IJPC-SE) works at the interface of research and policy. We strive to bring clarity to the science of epidemiology, paving the way to rational evidence-based policy. We work to promote and protect public health by serving as an ethical and effective counterweight to the misuse of epidemiology.

INEP is a not-for-profit consortium of 24 (at time of going to print) national and international volunteer, professional epidemiology organizations, spanning six continents, that have joined together to ensure health for all through ethical, independent and transparent science. It works collaboratively and transparently to address health-related issues and minimize harm. It hosts forums and develops position statements and policy briefs with recommendations to protect and improve public health. Through its collective efforts, INEP brings the benefit of a unified professional voice in the public interest.

Ultimately, rational policy will be influenced by evidence. The generation of evidence by trained scientists is expected to follow scientific and ethical principles such that valid science results. INEP (formerly IJPC-SE) was one of the endorsers of the 2017 Aircraft Cabin Air Quality Conference.

History of scientific misconduct and dishonesty

Misconduct and dishonesty in science have been known since the times of, among others, Galileo and Newton in the basic and physical sciences. The conventional wisdom of science being a strictly logical process, with objectivity the essence of scientists' attitudes, errors being speedily corrected by rigorous peer scrutiny and

replication, is an idealized construct. And, since the advent of applied health sciences, like epidemiology, the opportunities for misconduct and dishonesty have grown. Today, the driver of these likely is more the financial incentives rather than in former days when job security and glory may have been more what motivated such conduct.

The work of epidemiology involves navigating through all types of bias that influence research in public health. Because it is possible to manipulate experimental and control groups in ways that introduce bias and thus fail to serve the public interest through the pursuit of truth (as expected of scientists), it is ever more recognized that ethical training and oversight are crucial.

Our ethics and values determine in large part our behaviors and the choices that we make as scientists, being that scientists are also human and subject to human frailties. The four fundamental principles of bioethics, one being no more important than the other, are:

- *Respect for autonomy* – requires respect for individual rights and freedoms
- *Beneficence* – requires doing good
- *Non-maleficence* – requires doing no harm
- *Social and distributive justice* – requires the fair and equitable allocation of risks and benefits to all without discrimination

All biomedical studies must consider, in advance of any study, the impact of the study being proposed from the vantage point of these four principles. In public health research, additional principles apply and also must be considered, including the need to:

- *Protect the most vulnerable*
- *Engage with the community*
- *Apply the Precautionary Principle*, and
- *Conduct oneself with integrity*

In all of this, given the many competing interests involved in population and community health research, we must

not be naïve about the forces at play that influence both science and policy.

Great vigilance and personal integrity are required to counter the influence of financially interested parties and corrupt/morally bankrupt governments where a sizeable proportion of elected representatives are beholden to powerful moneyed interests. In particular, the seduction by moneyed interests in using academics to downplay or deny the seriousness of the hazards must be recognized. These are the studies that will infiltrate the scientific literature to cast doubt and foment uncertainty. Libraries of books and movies, including documentaries and docudramas, are accessible that have explored and exposed these misdeeds.

Biases that can be introduced into applied research, either wittingly or unwittingly, and that are counter to the public interest are:

- *Publication Bias* – selective material infiltrates the peer-reviewed literature
- *Suppression Bias* – questions/findings that upset powerful interests are suppressed
- *Repression Bias* – questions/findings that we know might upset powerful interests we refrain from asking/presenting
- *Funding Bias* – only that which powerful interests want studied will be studied

These and other biases, if allowed to go unchallenged, present the policy maker with a conundrum. By increasing uncertainty, the policy-maker's ability to implement health policy is made all the more difficult. The tobacco example is perhaps the best known in that it took some 50 years, and with many sick people and premature deaths along the way, before policy could be introduced to more effectively control people's access and exposure to tobacco. It has been demonstrated through freedom of information just how the industry mounted disinformation campaigns, lied, manipulated, and deceived both the public and policy makers, and how they co-opted or appropriated scientists to lie. The real tragedy is that, while business does what business

sees itself as needing to do to increase profits, scientists accept their money and then proceed to please their sponsor. We must remain vigilant as to whether this is what is happening in the area of cabin air quality.

How manipulation operates

When a scientist discovers a finding that does not support the *status quo* and goes contrary to the interests of a powerful stakeholder, the “Four D’s” are applied, in that what they are reporting will not result in action, but rather will be confronted with:

- *Deny* – denial that the findings could be correct;
- *Delay* – in that more research will be called for;
- *Divide* – in that commissioned work will result in biased findings; and
- *Discredit* – if the scientist persists, he/she will be discredited.

This paradigm (i.e., the “Four D’s”) was applied many times over in the case of each of the following substances before policy was ultimately changed:

- Tobacco
- Nickel
- Benzene
- Lead
- Asbestos
- Climate Change

The question now is: When will cabin air quality be rationally addressed, given that it has and continues to be subjected to the “FOUR D’s”?

For those who wittingly, and for large sums of money, prostitute themselves by casting aside their scientific values (i.e., the pursuit of truth in the public interest), a toolkit of techniques is available to them to skew results and contribute to the production of junk science:

- Under-powered studies
- Inadequate follow-up methods
- Inadequate follow-up time
- Inappropriate biomarkers of exposure
- Contaminated controls

- Unbalanced discussion
- Selective disclosure of competing interests
- Biased/selective interpretation
- Mechanistic information is ignored for inferring effects
- Exaggerated differences are made between human and toxicology studies, the insistence being on separating effects seen in animals from effects in humans
- The fact that molecular structures predicting hazard potential is ignored
- The insistence on first demonstrating effects in local populations of exposed people despite demonstrated effects in humans elsewhere
- The failure to make explicit the implicit value judgements that go into deciding appropriate standards of evidence for drawing policy-relevant conclusions (i.e., suppressing dominant interests and values)

Conformist thinking

To understand the role of influence and its impact, we must recognize that we all operate within the framework of:

- A dominant paradigm
- A contextual narrative

With this recognized, what role can impartial science play in the public interest?

Working at the nexus of research and policy, there are many forces, or drivers, at play in working to inform policy in order to maintain and improve population health. Ideology is one class of such drivers; financial conflicting interests is another. Both are integral to our personal contextual narratives (i.e., the dominant paradigm that defines the story of our lives: that which gives meaning to us as individuals in society, reducing our objectivity).

Leadership requires the ability to think beyond the constraints of the dominant paradigm. Yet, the pressures are relentless from vested interests that maneuver

their way onto review panels, influence boards of our professional associations, and infiltrate the published literature with junk science.

Expert witness tensions arise between the plaintiff and defense sides of the argument in tort actions where the rubber hits the road concerning policy decisions. Regarding engine and aircraft fluids — consisting of tricresyl phosphate (TCP), other hazardous substances, including by-products of pyrolysis — along with cases of fume events reported to date, and illness reports proximate to these events with observed long-term sequelae, the Precautionary Principle would seem warranted: “Where there is a risk from a certain agent, the presence of uncertainty shall not be used as a reason for postponing cost-effective measures to prevent such exposure.”

THE “FOUR D’s” classically applied to cabin air quality

Not only is the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) in DENIAL, they are DELAYING action by sponsoring further research. They deny any health effects from fume events, despite the reality of sick people resulting from such events with acute illness proximate to exposure events, and with longer-term effects seen in some cases; they dismiss “aerotoxic syndrome” as even possible. Their linear reductionist approach, invoking the argument of low-level OPC in cabins, appears to provide them the basis for ruling out any human health effects from fume events, and also from low-level exposure to cabin air, even in the absence of fume events.

Their bias toward finding no-effect is apparent in their project description using words such a “misguided” in ruling out alternative hypotheses in their study. One is left wondering if, with their approach, they will measure the most relevant exposures and endpoints.

Recent wisdom shared from Morris Greenberg tells us that, under the Precautionary Principle, “... *the discharge of gases and fumes into an aircraft cabin can be justified only after prior investigation finds the practice to be innocuous. The chemical cocktails to which passengers and crew are exposed will vary qualitatively and*

quantitatively, so that, even if a standard examination methodology has been employed, their effects need not be identical between incidents.”

From a human safety and health perspective, the obligation of the industry is to avoid supply air contaminating cabin air. With the design of one aircraft more recently, the problem has been largely avoided. Given what is already known, while more research may be of interest to advance knowledge to achieve greater precision in our estimates of effect, we have sufficient experience to act now to protect cabin crew, pilots, and passengers by engineering the problem out and acknowledge previous harms caused.

Of note, the German Airline Association’s Trade Group (BDL), among others, was invited to participate in this seminal conference. Their own Position Statement claims “*Regarding the topic of cabin air, it has repeatedly been stated in the past few years whether the health of the passengers and crews as well as the safety of the flight could be endangered by the penetration of burned oil residues into the cabin air. It is therefore important to the airlines to know whether there are actually reliable findings from scientific investigations that confirm these statements and whether there is a problem that necessitates changes in flight operations or the maintenance or manufacture of aircraft.”*

If BDL had seen a glaring inconsistency between its decision to not participate in this conference and with the above words, they may have aligned their actions with their words by sending a representative and some of the German aviation industry to participate in the conference. Instead, by boycotting or shunning an opportunity to have a seat at the table, the opportunity to advance science is denied. Science advances through transparent, open discussion, and access to data.

CONCLUSIONS

- Systemic, institutionalized bias constrains science to conform to the dominant paradigm;
- Susan Michaelis and team are to be saluted for their

leadership in moving us all beyond the confines of the dominant paradigm;

- We all lose when the trajectory on which we find ourselves is flawed and unsustainable;
- A WIN – WIN – WIN outcome is most likely when the pursuit of truth is sought with a mind open to adapting to empirical realities; and
- The GCAQE is leading to a favorable outcome in which flight safety, health, and corporate profits all win.

We must persistently hold corporate leaders' feet to the fire on their obligation to protect worker and passenger safety and health based on valid evidence, decency, common sense; only then will rational policy prevail.

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Disclosure

In the interests of transparency:

- I have served as an expert witness in litigation (not related to this topic) on behalf of plaintiffs in the past, monies from which generally went into a University-managed research account.
- As a professional legacy, between 2012 and 2016, I bankrolled the INEP (formerly known as IJPC-SE) to become a self-sustaining public interest charity serving as a veritable David vs. Goliath in the pursuit of truth against moneyed influence in health policy.
- My comments are my own and are not necessarily endorsed by INEP.